

BioSentile: A Deep Space Nanosatellite for Biological Research.

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RATIONALE & PREVIOUS WORK

Since the final Apollo mission, no person has left Earth's magnetic field and travelled beyond low Earth orbit (LEO). The majority of governmental and commercial space agencies have recently focused their efforts on human space exploration, and more recently, NASA has been working to establish in situ sustainability on the Moon in order to serve, among other goals, as a steppingstone to Mars. The deepspace radiation environment [1], which continues to be a serious concern and preparation for exploration beyond LEO, poses the biggest risks for such endeavours.

The radiation environment in space is made up of a variety of particle types and energies that can have an impact on living things, including photons, ions, and electrons.

While we are easily shielded from lower energy species because we are one of the few living organisms in space, high energy species, in particular heavy ions, can pierce significant shielding thicknesses.

Despite being in interplanetary space, the biologically relevant dose rate may be too low to pose any significant risks during lengthy space travel, though the solar particle event (SPE) may be to blame. Chronic: Extended exposures may eventually reach risky concentrations.

The radiation is omnidirectional when it is far from large buildings or natural bodies, so shielding must offer protection in all directions [2]. A far cry from the full complement found in space, terrestrial radiation facilities only offer one, or in the best cases, a few, types and/or energies of particles at a time [3].

The delivery of the dose is rapid, lasting only a few minutes to a few hours as opposed to days or months. Although no terrestrial facilities can currently replicate the biologically relevant space environment, the biological responses to many stimuli depend on the time-varying details of the perturbation dose rate, energy spectrum, and other factors.

To characterise the radiobiological risks of this environment, as well as to validate biological radiation induced damage models and to demonstrate the effectiveness of radiation shielding materials and strategies, deep spaceflight missions are required.

Ionizing radiation significantly hinders long-term human exploration and habitation of space, especially beyond the magnetic field of Earth. The variety of highly energetic particles found in deep space can

have a number of harmful effects on living things. Many of these effects involve a carefully orchestrated chain of actions that are boosted by endogenous signalling and end with oxidative damage to DNA, lipids, proteins, and many metabolites [4].

Additionally, ionising radiation can cause direct DNA damage, such as double-strand DNA breaks (DSBs), a biological characteristic of ionising radiation that has been extensively studied [5]–[7]. Double-strand DNA breaks in eukaryotic organisms with nuclei are correctly repaired by homologous recombination, a highly conserved pathway that functions in the presence of other significant evolutionary changes (HR). The RAD52 epistasis group of genes, which code for a number of sensor and effector proteins as well as an intricate network of protein interactions, are crucial for HR [8]. Ionizing radiation has additional complex effects on higher eukaryotes like humans and small animals, including but not limited to gross chromosomal aberrations that can impair language, cognition, vision, cardiovascular damage, and cancer [4], [9]. radiation's effects on human space exploration of the solar system and beyond Not only was the Apollo-17 mission in 1972 the last to visit the Moon, but it was also the longest stay outside of Low Earth Orbit (LEO), lasting 12.5 days. Studies comparing modern LEO astronauts to beyond-LEO (bLEO) astronauts from the Apollo era have found that the Apollo cohort developed cardiovascular disease and cataracts at significantly higher rates, which have been linked to the effects of bLEO ionising radiation [10], [11]. The use of single- and mixed-ion species provided by particle-accelerator facilities in current radiation effects research for the preparation of long-duration missions and/or space habitation takes into account the lack of fidelity to space dose rate and energy distribution.

BIOSENTILE: NANOSTATS FOR DEEP SPACE BIOLOGICAL EXPERIMENTS.

Fully autonomous instruments, such as those supported by CubeSats, offer a low-cost, frequently available way to conduct meaningful research in space using human-relevant model organisms. It is nearly impossible to replicate all aspects of the space radiation environment by using terrestrial facilities, coupled with a probable lack of human tending of many future science experiments conducted beyond LEO (Woellert et al., 2011).

GeneSat-1 (Ricco et al., 2007), Organism/Organic Exposure to Orbital Stresses (O/OREOS) (Nicholson et al., 2011; Nicholson and Ricco, 2020), PharmaSat (Parra et al., 2008; Ricco et al., 2011), SporeSat (Park et al., 2017), and other biological CubeSats have recently been developed and flow The EcAMSat (E. coli AntiMicrobial Satellite) (Matin et al., Padgen et al., 2020a; 2017). The biological subjects used in these missions included *Escherichia coli* (multiple strains), *Bacillus subtilis* (multiple strains), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and *Ceratopteris richardii*. PharmaSat and EcAMSat also supported drug dose-response experiments. All of the setups, which is interesting, flew in LEO to conduct their experiments and transmit the data they collected to one or more ground stations. All but SporeSat used microfluidics systems to deliver growth media and precisely mix reagents, and the experiments required cartridges to keep the cells in a state of stasis from loading until the start of the experiment, which was frequently several weeks to months (Massaro Tieze et al., 2020).

By their very nature, CubeSats are limited in terms of mass, size, and power. The free-flying 3U satellites GeneSat-1, O/OREOS, PharmaSat, and SporeSat each had a capacity for 2U of payload. (1U = 10 cm cube). The biological samples, all auxiliary fluidic hardware, electronics for fluidic and thermal

control, optical measurements, and data handling were all contained in the 2U payloads. The EcAMSat (E. coli AntiMicrobial Satellite) (Matin et al., Padgen et al., 2020a; 2017). The biological subjects used in these missions included *Escherichia coli* (multiple strains), *Bacillus subtilis* (multiple strains), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and *Ceratopteris richardii*. PharmaSat and EcAMSat also supported drug dose-response experiments. EcAMSat was NASA's first 6U CubeSat to be launched from the ISS; the additional surface area allowed for the mission's increased power requirements (Padgen et al., 2020a, 2020b). Magnets and hysteresis rods were carried by the remaining 3U in that satellite for passive flight orientation.

The two 6U Mars Cube One (MarCO) CubeSats recently showed that small satellites are capable of performing deep space missions (Klesh et al., 2018). Although these are the only CubeSats that have been launched beyond low-Earth orbit (LEO), thirteen 6U satellites with a variety of secondary payloads will launch shortly aboard NASA's Space Launch System Artemis 1 rocket, formerly known as Exploration Mission 1 or EM-1 (Robinson et al., 2018). BioSentinel was the first interplanetary biological CubeSat, the only biological mission among all the nanostats and cubesats, and the first livebiology experiment carried out outside the Earth-Moon system (Massaro Tieze et al., 2020). (Ricco et al., 2020).

The larger of the two scientific payloads that will be carried into heliocentric orbit by the BioSentinel spacecraft—the one that is the focus of this article—the so-called BioSensor payload—monitors DNA damage and repair using yeasts.

A second payload is a tiny spectrometer that is integrated onto a single printed-circuit board to measure and catalogue the linear-energy-transfer (LET) characteristics of individual radiation events for a continuous cataloguing of ionising impacts on its detector by particles or photons (Kroupa et al., 2015) which, when a specific experimental time point is obtained, allow the cumulative history of BioSentinel's physical radiation environment over the course of the mission to be compared and correlated with the biological effects recorded by the BioSensor payload (Ricco et al., 2020). BioSentinel was created to show how long-duration, deep-space nanosatellite1 missions enable research on how the genuine space environment affects living things in order to inform countermeasures like therapies and strategies, both technological and biomedical, to help astronauts cope with the effects of their environment in the future missions to the Moon and deep space.

Sending terrestrial organisms to live beyond the radiation barrier of Earth's magnetic field and observing their reactions is how NASA's BioSentinel mission is the first step in an emerging effort to understand the impacts of the deep-space environment in situ. The BioSentinel Nanosatellite is a six-unit deep-space cubesat that contains microorganisms that are developed and characterised in relation to the type and amount of radiation to which they are exposed over the course of three years. It is the only biological mission on NASA's Artemis-1, which will be launched into space using the Space Launch System (SLS). After the Orion capsule separates, BioSentinel will be launched on a trajectory that will take it past the moon and into a (permanent) heliocentric orbit far from the magnetic field and radiation belts of Earth. Comparing the radiation environments of deep space, LEO, and Earth will be possible thanks to a companion mission that is planned to operate in LEO aboard the International Space Station (ISS), safely within the geomagnetic field, with an identical ground-control payload. The three locations also provide controls for effects related to two gravitational environments, namely micro-g (on ISS and the BioSentinel Nanosatellite) and terrestrial gravity.

BioSentinel was created using the "canary in the coal mine" strategy, which involved using a model organism that had many similarities to humans to evaluate and investigate the health risk for long-duration human missions beyond LEO. The most crucial factor is the point at which DNA double strand

breaks occur and how well they are repaired. The model eukaryote *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (*S. cerevisiae*), or budding yeast, was carried in BioSentinel's payload.

Yeast is relevant to understanding human well-being in space because yeast and humans share a strong conservation of gene function. This genetic overlap is highlighted by the fact that a significant number of crucial yeast genes are so similar to human genes that they can be substituted for human counterparts [12]. A dormant, desiccated form of yeast cells was placed inside microfluidic "minicards" and sent into deep space. *Cerevisiae* was chosen for BioSentinel due to its ease of genetic manipulation, spaceflight history, and similarity to human cells, particularly in the repair of DSBs via the HR pathway. Moreover, a wild-type strain of yeast and a mutant strain were chosen to be aboard BioSentinel. The mutant strain's RAD51 gene, which expresses the Rad51 recombinase protein, an important part of DSB HR repair, has been deleted, rendering it incapable of performing DNA repair. The so-called rad51D mutant is unable to repair radiation-induced DNA damage, in contrast to the wild-type strain, which is skilled at doing so and serves as a healthy control. The second payload of BioSentinel is a physical radiation spectrometer with a dosimeter function, which records the concurrent "space weather"—time-varying details of the ambient radiation environment. In addition to measuring the total ionising dose, it will also describe the linear-energy-transfer (LET) characteristics of individual radiation events in real time (TID). The first direct, time-resolved, in-situ correlation of measured biological responses with radiation dosimetry and spectroscopy in deep space will be made possible by BioSentinel. 13 6U nanosatellites will be mounted between the Interim Cryogenic Propulsion Stage (ICPS) and the Orion crew vehicle on the SLS Artemis-1 vehicle as secondary payloads. Astronauts will be transported by SLS to places like Mars, the moon, asteroids, and the Earth's Lagrange (libration) points. The goal of Artemis-1 is to place the (uncrewed) Orion capsule on a circumlunar trajectory, where it will travel for 25 days before returning to Earth on its own.

The SLS upper stage performs a disposal manoeuvre after Orion separates to place it in a heliocentric orbit without the possibility of a subsequent collision with Earth, the moon, or a spacecraft orbiting either one. After this manoeuvre is complete, the secondary nanosats will launch from the upper stage over the course of several days at various "bus stops," Image 2. Approximately 37 000 km from Earth, in the outer Van Allen radiation belt, BioSentinel will deploy as soon as it is possible (4 hours after launch). From there, its trajectory will take it to a 700 km flyby of the moon and then to a stable heliocentric orbit that is slightly different from Earth's.

Due to its different orbital radius, BioSentinel will gradually distance itself from Earth. Due to this relative motion, the BioSentinel's ranges from Earth are 0.2 astronomical units (AU) at its 6-month nominal mission duration and 0.4 AU (60 million km) at its 9-month extended mission duration. Science objectives of BioSentinel. A "quiet" microgravity environment and a state of orbital freefall are expected to be provided by BioSentinel. The following will be the only vibrational or inertial acceleration-induced perturbations to microgravity aboard BioSentinel, in comparison to the International Space Station (ISS), with its crew movements and the operation of life-support and other machinery: initial detumbling after deployment; sporadic micropropulsive desaturation of reaction wheels; the reaction wheels themselves; and, for periods of a few minutes at a time, opening and closing of miniature fluid valves and operation of a miniature peristaltic pump. The satellite will rotate to point its antennae towards Earth during communications passes. The spacecraft will generally maintain a relatively constant orientation with solar panels facing the sun and its "cold side" (see below) in shadow. Galactic cosmic radiation (GCR), estimated at 6.9 cGy over 6 months, and SPEs, which must be estimated probabilistically due to the unpredictability of the sun, in particular the number and magnitude of SPEs it generates in any given time period [15], make up the anticipated total-dose radiation environment for BioSentinel. For instance, there is a 50% chance that SPEs will deliver at least 13 cGy

to the payloads for a shielding thickness of 3.7 mm (or 1 g/cm²) of aluminium; there is a 25% chance that they will deliver at least 50 cGy, and there is a 10% chance that they will deliver 150 cGy [15]. The dose from SPEs becomes insignificant in relation to the probability at the other end of the scale (invariant).

CONCLUSION:

With the exception of a few expensive, human-operated bLEO missions, studying biology's reaction to the complex interplanetary space radiation environment directly has never been attempted. However, if humans are to travel outside of Earth's protective magnetic field for periods longer than a few days, such studies are essential. This paradigm is about to change, and BioSentinel is the leading example of a class of reliable, autonomous bioanalytical microsystems that are compatible with small satellites.

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